

TEACHING THE STEPS OF CREATING ANIMATION TO STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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In the conditions of globalization, taking into account the need and suggestions for improving efficiency in the fields of education, production and service, training competitive personnel, and making quality products, the development of students' creative ability and design knowledge with the help of computers is considered as a very urgent issue. After all, nowadays, activities in the fields of education, service and production are carried out almost on the basis of computer technology.

For example, by the end of the first half of 2021, the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 318.5 trillion. 23.1%, i.e. 73.6 trillion. (\$67,727,309) amounts to soums. Now 2021 is seen in the world's highest-grossing cartoon "Little Boss 2", whose income was \$948,550,636. It can be seen that the income of the cartoon "Little Boss 2" is 14 times greater than the share of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in the GDP. On the other hand, if a maximum of 70 workers work to create a cartoon, the abundance of labor for the development of agriculture, forestry and fisheries will help the development of animation, computer animation and multiplication education in Uzbekistan to find its place at the international level.

We can understand that the animation recognized by N.N.Yaroshenko encourages full recreation, educational, cultural and social activities in the process of spending free time. Its premise is that people use their leisure time for cultural self-development and self-awareness. The term "animation" appears for the first time in French. In the dictionary of the 19th and 20th centuries (Paris, 1974), animation is defined as the act of giving life, breathing life.

K.N.Chou believes that "animation is a sequence of still images or cartoons that create the illusion of movement among people".

Animation (lat. Animare - to animate) is a type of art, the works of which are created by photographing individual drawings or scenes frame by frame. In addition to the term "animation", the term "multiplication" is also widely used (Latin multiplicatio - multiplication).

Animation has its own history, so E. Reino is the creator of the technology of performing caricatures frame by frame. But animation was most used during the Walt Disney era. The animation principles he used were so effective that they are still considered the foundation of the animator. There are several types of

animation: traditional, computer. Computer and traditional are essentially the same thing, only traditional is drawn by hand on paper, and computer is drawn on a tablet, in some program. Animation is a complex process that takes a lot of time. Traditional animation takes the most time to complete, so it is rarely used now. In computer animation, everything is much simpler.

Computer animation is a type of animation created by a computer. Unlike the common concept of "CGI graphics", which refers to both still and moving images, computer animation refers only to moving images. Today, it is widely used in entertainment, industry, science and business. Animation, a derivative of computer graphics, uses the same methods of creating images: vector graphics, raster graphics, fractal graphics, three-dimensional graphics (3D).

When teaching computer animation to students, animation creation was divided into three stages: animation-concept stage, visual-design stage, 3D composition stage.

Animated-ideal stage. The first stage of the production of animated films begins with the basic concepts embodied in the form of full animations, and then, after the animation is brought to its final form, work begins on other components of the film, for example, the script, scenes, selection types. cameras etc.

One of the main components of the pre-production stage of animated films is storyboards, mockups, model sheets or model sheets and animatics (rough animations, storyboards in motion).

Visual design stage. Now that the storyboard has been approved by the bosses, the project will enter the production stage. This is where the actual work on the film begins, based on the plan established during pre-production. One of the most important parts of this phase is layouts, modeling, texturing, lighting, rigging, and animation.

3D composition stage. This stage is the third and final stage of filmmaking, and it refers to the tasks that must be completed after filming is completed. These tasks include editing raw footage for cutscenes, adding transitions between shots, working with sound, dubbing actors – just a few of the countless tasks people face in post-production.

